

PRIVACY PRESERVING SOCIAL MEDIA DATA PUBLISHING FOR PERSONALIZED RANKING BASED RECOMMENDATION

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Abstract— A personalised recommendation is essential to assisting users in finding relevant information. To mine user preferences, it frequently uses a sizable collection of user data, particularly information about users' online behaviour (such as tagging, rating, and check-ins on social media). While private information (such as gender) may frequently be deduced from user activity data, exposing such data exposes users to inference attacks. In this research, we introduced Priv Rank, a continuous privacy-preserving social media data publishing architecture that allows for tailored ranking-based recommendations while defending users against inference assaults. Its main concept is to continuously obfuscate user activity data in order to limit the privacy leakage of user-specified private data within a certain data distortion budget. This also limits the ranking loss brought on by the data obfuscation process in order to preserve the utility of the data for enabling recommendations.

INTRODUCTION

In the Big Data era, building efficient recommendation engines is essential to giving people the right information. Online services, including e-commerce applications, typically rely on a sizable collection of user data, particularly user activity data from social media, like tagging/rating records, comments, check-ins, or other types of user activity data, to deliver high-quality and personalised recommendations. In reality, a lot of consumers are open to giving a service provider access to their social media activity data in exchange for receiving individualised, high-quality recommendations.

Such user activity data are referred to as public data in this essay. But people frequently view certain information from their social media profiles as private, like their gender, income, political leanings, or social ties. These data are referred to as private data in the text that follows. Users may choose not to disclose private information, but the inherent correlation between public and private information frequently results in serious privacy leakage. For instance, one's gender can be inferred from her actions on location-based social networks [2] and one's political allegiance can be deduced from her TV show ratings [1]. These studies demonstrate that inference attacks [3], in which an adversary examines a user's public data to illicitly learn about her private data, frequently cause harm to private data.

Therefore, it is essential to safeguard user private information while providing recommendation engines with public data. Privacy-preserving data publishing has received a lot of attention in an effort to solve this issue[4]. Its core concept aims to secure private data by falsifying public data before it is published, but at the risk of losing the usefulness of the public data later in the processing process. Utility in the context of recommendation engines refers to how well they do personalisation based on distorted public data, or more specifically, how well they are able to forecast a person's preferences based on distorted data. Privacy and personalisation are inherently in conflict. On the one hand, greater data distortion improves privacy protection by making it more difficult for adversaries to deduce personal information. However, it also results in a greater loss of usefulness because severely skewed public data make it impossible for recommendation engines to correctly predict users' preferences.

One quick solution is to obfuscate user public data before it is sent to social media in order to apply privacy-preserving data publishing techniques in the case of social media-based recommendation. Such a strategy is unrealistic, though, as it undermines important user benefits. In practical applications, social media gives users a platform for social sharing through which they can communicate with their peers by wilfully disclosing their thoughts on products, blogs, pictures, videos, or even their current whereabouts.

For instance, a user who enjoyed a film and wants to recommend it to her friends does not want the rating to be obscured in any way.

Since it is improper to obscure user public data prior to being Protecting user privacy when distributing their public data from social media to any other third-party services is an alternative to releasing it to social media. In order to supply them with data, several third-party social media services specifically want access to user activity data (or data streams). These services may also request optional access to user profiles. While some users who care about privacy choose to keep some information from their profiles secret (such as gender), other users who don't care about privacy may not care about the same type of private information and opt to share it. By discovering the association between the public and private data from the non-privacy conscious users, an attacker might then improperly infer the private data of the privacy-conscious users. Consequently, it is indispensable to provide privacy protection when releasing user public data from social media.

EXISTING SYSTEM

The current practise generally relies on regulations or user agreements, such as those on the use and storage of the published data, to guarantee user privacy while publishing user data. This strategy, however, cannot ensure that a hostile attacker won't gain access to the users' sensitive data. Therefore, privacy-preserving data publishing has been extensively researched in order to offer appropriate privacy protection when releasing user data. Its fundamental concept is to obfuscate user data so that it can be released and still be relevant in specific application circumstances while maintaining the privacy of the user. Existing work can be divided into two categories based on the attacks taken into consideration. The first group relies on heuristic methods to safeguard the privacy of users who have made specific requests. Particular remedies primarily address the privacy threat that arises when attackers are able to link the data owner's identity to a record, or an attribute in the published data. The second category is theory-based and focuses on the uninformative principle, i.e., on the fact that the published data should provide attackers with as little additional information as possible beyond background knowledge.

DISADVANTAGES

- Privacy is less.
- Performance is low.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system proposes Priv Rank, a customizable and continuous privacy preserving data publishing framework protect users against inference attacks while enabling personalized ranking-based recommendation. It provides continuous protection of user-specified private data against inference attacks by obfuscating both the historical and streaming user activity data before releasing them, while still preserving the utility of the published data for enabling personalized ranking-based recommendation by efficiently limiting the pair wise ranking loss incurred from data obfuscation.

ADVANTAGES

- Privacy is more.
- Performance is better.

MODULES

SERVICE PROVIDER

In this module, the SP has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can perform some operations, such as Upload Products, View all uploaded Products, View Rating Results, View Dislikes results, View Rank Results, View all Remote Users, View All product reviews, View Trending products, View Products Recommends.

USER

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before performing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user can perform some operations like Search Products, View All Products Reviews, View Trending Products, View Your Profiles, View Recommended products.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE-

This paper introduced Priv Rank, a customizable and continuous privacy-preserving social media data publishing framework. It continuously protects user-specified data against inference attacks by releasing obfuscated user activity data, while still ensuring the utility of the released data to power personalized ranking-based recommendations. To provide customized protection, the optimal data obfuscation is learned such that the privacy leakage of user-specified private data is minimized ;to provide continuous privacy protection, we consider both the historical and online activity data publishing; to ensure the data utility for enabling ranking-based recommendation, we bound the ranking loss incurred from the data obfuscation process using the Kendall-rank distance.

We showed through extensive experiments that Priv Rank can provide an efficient and effective protection of private data, while still preserving the utility of the published data for different ranking-based recommendation use cases.

In the future, we plan to extend our framework by considering the data types with continuous values rather than discretized values, and explore further data utility beyond personalized recommendation.

REFERENCES-

- [1] S. Salamatian, A. Zhang, F. du Pin Calmon, S. Bhamidipati, N. Fawaz, B. Kveton, P. Oliveira, and N. Taft, "How to hide the elephant-or the donkey-in the room: Practical privacy against statistical inference for large data," in Proc. of GlobalSIP. IEEE, 2013.
- [2] D. Yang, D. Zhang, Q. Bingqing, and P. Cudre-Mauroux, "Privcheck: Privacy- preserving check-in data publishing for personalized location-based services," in Proc. of UbiComp'16. ACM, 2016.
- [3] C. Li, H. Shirani-Mehr, and X. Yang, "Protecting individual information against inference attacks in data publishing," in Advances in Databases: Concepts, Systems and Applications. Springer, 2007, pp. 422–433.
- [4] B. Fung, K. Wang, R. Chen, and P. S. Yu, "Privacy-preserving data publishing: A survey of recent developments," ACM Computer Survey, vol. 42, no. 4, p. 14, 2010.
- [5] I. A. Junglas, N. A. Johnson, and C. Spitzmüller, "Personality traits and concern for privacy: an empirical study in the context of location-based services," European Journal of Information Systems, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 387–402, 2008.
- [6] P. Cremonesi, Y. Koren, and R. Turrin, "Performance of recommender algorithms on top-n recommendation tasks," in Proc. of RecSys'10. ACM, 2010, pp. 39–46.
- [7] N. Li, R. Jin, and Z.-H. Zhou, "Top rank optimization in linear time," in Advances in neural information processing systems, 2014, pp. 1502–1510.
- [8] M. G. Kendall, "Rank correlation methods." 1948.
- [9] L. Sweeney, "k-anonymity: A model for protecting privacy," International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based
- [10] L. Sankar, S. R. Rajagopalan, and H. V. Poor, "Utility-privacy tradeoffs in databases: An information-theoretic approach," IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security, vol. 8, no. 6, pp.838–852, 2013.
- [11] A. Machanavajjhala, D. Kifer, J. Gehrke, and M. Venkatasubramanian, "l-diversity: Privacy beyond k-anonymity," ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 3, 2007.
- [12] C. Dwork, "Differential privacy," in Automata, languages and programming. Springer, 2006, pp. 1–12.
- [13] F. du Pin Calmon and N. Fawaz, "Privacy against statistical inference," in Proc. of Allerton'12. IEEE, 2012, pp. 1401–1408.
- [14] A. Zhang, S. Bhamidipati, N. Fawaz, and B. Kveton, "Priview: Media consumption and recommendation meet privacy against inference attacks," IEEE Web, vol. 2, 2014.
- [15] S. Salamatian, A. Zhang, F. du Pin Calmon, S. Bhamidipati, N. Fawaz, B. Kveton, P. Oliveira, and N. Taft, "Managing your private and public data: Bringing down inference attacks against your privacy," IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing, vol. 9, no. 7, pp. 1240–1255, 2015.
- [16] W. Chen, T.-Y. Liu, Y. Lan, Z.-M. Ma, and H. Li, "Ranking measures and loss functions in learning to rank," in Proc. of NIPS, 2009, pp. 315–323.
- [17] M. B. Eisen, P. T. Spellman, P. O. Brown, and D. Botstein, "Cluster analysis and display of genome-wide expression patterns," PNAS, vol. 95, no. 25, pp. 14 863–14 868, 1998.
- [18] R. Baeza-Yates, B. Ribeiro-Neto et al., Modern information retrieval ACM press New York, 1999, vol. 463.